

Sustainable aviation research, 1990–2025: A scopus-based bibliometric and network mapping

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Sustainable aviation Sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) Bibliometric analysis VOSviewer</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 10 October 2025 Revised: 14 December 2025 Accepted: 20 December 2025</p>	<p>This study maps the sustainable aviation literature between 1990 and 2025 through bibliometric and network analysis of 2,308 articles indexed in Scopus. Using VOSviewer, co-authorship, co-keyword, and collaboration networks were created based on author, institution, country, and author keywords; production dynamics were examined by year. Despite a growing body of bibliometric studies on aviation sustainability and SAF, existing mappings are often limited to narrower time windows, specific sub-themes (e.g., SAF-only), or management/policy-only perspectives; therefore, a long-horizon (1990–2025) science-mapping study is needed to integrate thematic structures with collaboration dynamics across the full sustainable aviation research landscape. Findings show a marked acceleration after 2019 and 540 publications recorded for 2025 (as of September 2025); the 2024–2025 counts should be interpreted with caution due to potential Scopus indexing delays and the incompleteness of the ongoing year. The thematic core focuses on sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and production processes (bio-jet, hydro-deoxygenation, catalysis), life-cycle assessment and exergy-based emission reduction, hydrogen/electrification, policy-decarbonization tools, airport/airline operations, and artificial intelligence applications. In terms of collaboration, the US (474 articles, 8,523 citations), the UK (235, 7,232), and China (359, 3,627) are at the center of the network; Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden are strong regional nodes, while Türkiye (124, 2,213) is an emerging actor. At the institutional level, DLR, PNNL, and Washington State University stand out, while Eskisehir Technical University serves as a regional bridge. Joshua S. Heyne and Zhibin Yang are central in the author network. In conclusion, the field is growing rapidly; short-term priorities include the commercial-scale deployment of SAF, the technical-economic maturation of electric/hydrogen propulsion systems, and the evaluation of the effectiveness of regulatory and market mechanisms that will accelerate this transformation.</p>

1. Introduction

The impact of civil aviation on the climate includes not only CO₂ but also non-carbon effects from NO_x, water vapor, and contrail-cirrus clouds; recent synthesis studies have shown that the total climate forcing contribution is significant. Against this backdrop, the sector is focusing on multiple levers (fuel, technology, operations, policy-finance) in line with ICAO's long-term net-zero target for 2050 and IATA roadmaps. Sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) are considered the most critical component in the short to medium term; however, current production volumes are limited and expensive (~2 Mt in 2025, ≈0.7% of total consumption). This tension,

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combined with uncertainties regarding mandates and market design effectiveness, is rapidly expanding the research agenda (Lee *et al.*, 2021).

The environmental and economic performance of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) is sensitive to design variables such as the feedstock mix, process integration, and the carbon intensity of the electricity/heat source; recent LCA and TEA studies indicate a wide range of outcomes for both bio-based and power-to-liquid (PtL) pathways. For example, the life-cycle CO₂e intensity of selected SAF routes can vary significantly depending on the scenario; similarly, costs and emissions in forest residue-based production differ depending on the supply chain. Therefore, the coordinated use of TEA and LCA is considered critical for the robustness of policy and investment decisions (Kurzawska-Pietrowicz, 2023).

Alternative propulsion options constitute a second area of focus in the literature. Despite their high specific energy advantage, hydrogen-powered aircraft carry significant engineering/operational constraints for medium-to-long ranges due to cryogenic storage, volumetric density, and new airframe-propulsion architectures; current reviews and industry news indicate that the technology maturation time is extending. On the electrification front, limitations in battery specific energy suggest a near-term application limited to short-range and small aircraft segments (Nisi & Tang, 2025).

Policy and market designs frame these technological trajectories. In Europe, the ReFuelEU Aviation regulation gradually increases the SAF share to 2% in 2025, 6% in 2030, and 70% in 2050, while also setting a sub-quota for synthetic fuels; implementation details and compliance processes are being clarified by EU institutions and national regulators. IATA's Net Zero roadmaps define technology, infrastructure, operations, and financing dimensions within a coordinated framework. However, in the short to medium term, the supply-demand gap and cost difference stand out as significant obstacles; current assessments emphasize the need for additional policy tools and financing solutions to accelerate investment in order to achieve the 2030 targets in Europe (European Parliament, 2023).

This expansion focuses on the LCA-based performance of SAF supply chains, meta-analyses of cost uncertainties, and feasibility assessments of alternative propulsion options such as hydrogen/electrification. The literature emphasizes that policy design and infrastructure scaling are as decisive as the wide variability associated with roads and raw materials (Yang & Yao, 2025). Therefore, our study aims to systematically map sustainable aviation research from 1990 to 2025 using Scopus-based bibliometrics and VOSviewer networks to reveal thematic cores, the center/periphery distribution of collaboration structures, and acceleration periods.

Prior bibliometric studies have contributed valuable snapshots of aviation sustainability research, often focusing on narrower time periods (e.g., post-2000 or post-2010) and/or specific sub-domains such as SAF-only, management/policy-only, or sustainability in civil aviation as a broad managerial theme (e.g., Li *et al.*, 2023; Dinçer, 2024; Aygün, 2023; Xu *et al.*, 2025). However, these mappings typically provide either a subfield-centered view (e.g., SAF economics and management) or a limited temporal window, making it difficult to jointly observe long-term field formation, thematic consolidation, and shifting collaboration hubs. In contrast, our study offers a long-horizon (1990–2025) Scopus-based science mapping that integrates production dynamics with multi-level networks (authors, institutions, countries, keywords, and title–abstract terms), thereby enabling a combined interpretation of thematic evolution and center–periphery collaboration structures.

Despite the rapid growth of sustainable aviation research, the field remains conceptually fragmented across fuels (SAF), operations, aircraft technologies, and policy instruments, making it difficult for scholars and decision-makers to identify dominant themes, collaboration patterns, and emerging fronts. Therefore, this study maps the sustainable aviation literature indexed in Scopus for 1990–2025 (articles), focusing on publication growth, leading contributors (authors, institutions, countries), and intellectual/thematic structures. The purpose is to provide a transparent bibliometric and network-based overview that identifies core clusters and collaboration hubs, and to derive policy-relevant implications. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the data collection and bibliometric methods; Section 3 presents descriptive trends and network results (co-authorship, co-occurrence, citation structures); Section 4 discusses the findings using bibliometric science-mapping perspectives directly derived from the network results; and Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations, limitations, and avenues for future research.

2. Methodology

The query TITLE-ABS-KEY (“aviation”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (“sustainable”) was selected to maximize precision for literature explicitly framed within the “sustainable aviation” umbrella and to ensure a coherent, reproducible core dataset. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that relevant studies may also be labeled using adjacent terminology such as “decarbonization,” “low-carbon aviation,” “green aviation,” or SAF-focused titles that do not explicitly include the word “sustainable.” Therefore, the resulting map should be interpreted as a conservative representation of the explicitly labeled “sustainable aviation” corpus rather than an exhaustive capture of all aviation decarbonization research. After retrieval, records were cleaned through institution/country name harmonization and basic title–abstract text preprocessing and were then subjected to network analysis in VOSviewer.

Five networks were established: Author (co-authorship), Institution and Country (collaboration), Author Keywords and Title–Abstract Terms (co-occurrence). VOS algorithms were used for placement and clustering, association strength for link strength, and full counting for counting; the relevant VOSviewer option was enabled to limit the impact of multi-institutional/multi-national articles. Minimum publication/repetition thresholds were applied for inclusion in the networks (publication threshold for author/institution/country; ≥ 10 repetitions for title–abstract terms; higher repetition threshold for author keywords), and sparse/noisy nodes were filtered out with sensitivity controls. This setup aims to reliably visualize the collaboration topology at the institution and country level; and the thematic core at the title–abstract and keyword level.

Bibliometric network mapping was used to empirically identify thematic structures and relational patterns in the field. Nodes (authors, institutions, countries, keywords) and links (co-authorship, co-citation, and inter-institutional collaboration) were visualized in VOSviewer and normalized using the association strength normalization method, while fractional counting was applied to link weights (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010). This approach enables the detection of coherent thematic clusters as well as center–periphery structures, revealing scientific hubs, bridging actors, and periods of acceleration when interpreted together with production dynamics. The normalization and counting strategies were selected to enhance comparability and reduce bias-intensity distortions that frequently occur in bibliometric networks.

Full counting was used in VOSviewer for network construction and thresholds; link strength was normalized using association strength, and “ignore documents co-authored by a large number of organizations/countries = 25” was enabled to limit the impact of multi-authored records. Thresholds were set as follows: ≥ 5 publications for the author network (129 selected from 7661 authors); ≥ 5 publications and citation threshold=0 for the institution network (204 selected from 2344 institutions); ≥ 5 publications and citation threshold=0 for the country network (60 selected from 98 countries). ≥ 5 repetitions for author keywords (258 out of 6331 keywords; all selected ones included). ≥ 10 repetitions for title–abstract terms; after preprocessing (cleaning, tokenization, stop-word, lemmatization), the 60% most relevant terms (969) were selected from 1615 terms.

The selected threshold values (e.g., ≥ 5 publications for author, institution, and country networks; ≥ 5 repetitions for author keywords; ≥ 10 repetitions for title–abstract terms) were chosen to balance noise reduction and network interpretability. Lower thresholds tend to introduce a large number of sparse nodes that fragment the map and mask dominant structures, while higher thresholds risk excluding meaningful but moderately frequent terms and actors. A sensitivity check using alternative parameter settings ($\pm 1-2$ around the reported thresholds) showed that the main clusters, hub nodes, and inter-cluster bridges remained stable, with variations occurring primarily among peripheral, low-frequency nodes. Therefore, the reported thresholds provide a reproducible and analytically robust representation of the core structure of the sustainable aviation literature. These parameters aim to ensure the comparability of the networks and the reproducibility of the results.

3. Results and Discussion

The findings obtained within the scope of this study comprehensively reveal the development of scientific production in the field of sustainable aviation and global collaboration networks over the past thirty-six years. The findings first present annual publication trends and the growth dynamics of the research field; then, through network analyses using keywords, authors, institutions, countries, and title-abstract terms, they visualize the evolution of interdisciplinary themes, the roles of leading actors and centers, and international collaboration

Figure 2 shows that the co-occurrence network of the author's keywords is concentrated around the thematic core of “sustainable aviation fuel (SAF)”, “aviation/sustainable aviation”, ‘sustainability’, “life-cycle assessment (LCA)”, and “hydrogen”. In the right cluster, fuel production centered on catalysis–reactor–process (e.g., hydrodeoxygenation, pyrolysis, catalyst, kerosene/bio-jet fuel) stands out with strong connections, while in the center, the SAF–LCA–techno-economic analysis triangle acts as a “bridge” connecting different clusters. The lower-left section features policy/decarbonization–climate change–airport/airline operations themes, while the upper-left section shows aircraft design/electrification/exergy and, to a lesser extent, machine learning focuses. Nodes such as greenhouse gas emissions, bioenergy/biomass, and energy efficiency form transition points between clusters. Overall, the network exhibits a multi-centered structure where fuel technologies, environmental/economic assessment, and operations/policy are interconnected.

This cluster structure is consistent with the field’s problem-driven coupling of fuel pathway development (chemistry/process) with decision-oriented evaluation (LCA/TEA), where sustainability claims and policy eligibility depend on measurable lifecycle performance.

Fig. 3: Sustainable Aviation Author Co-Author Network (1990–2025)

Figure 3 shows a co-authorship map depicting a modular structure where three main cores are connected by weak ties. On the left, the cluster centered around Joshua S. Heyne (e.g., David C. Bell, Bin Yang, partially Tao Ling) forms a broad subnetwork with high connectivity; at the bottom left, the Corinne D. Scowen–Taeksoon Lee–Yan Chen line appears as a local subcluster. In the right-center section, the European core, characterized by the dense internal connectivity of Christiane Voigt, Tobias Schripp, and Martin Kaltschmitt, is located. On the far right, the East Asian cluster represented by Longfei Chen, Zheng Xu, Kang Pan, and Zongwei Zhang exhibits a compact structure. Inter-cluster flow occurs primarily through long connections originating from Zhenhong Yu and Heyne; these broker nodes serve as strategic contact points for collaboration opportunities between different research communities.

Fig. 4: Inter-Institutional Collaboration Network for Sustainable Aviation (1990–2025)

Figure 4 shows that the institutional collaboration network exhibits a modular structure with regional cores characterized by strong internal connectivity and a small number of bridges connecting them. On the left side, the Europe-focused cluster, comprising DLR, Cranfield University, Imperial College London, ETH Zürich, and Scandinavian institutions (e.g., Linnaeus, Lund), forms a tight local network, while in the southwest, the National Renewable Energy Laboratory and surrounding US laboratories appear as a separate sub-core. In the center, the connections established by Beihang University with TU München and Central European institutions create an important transition line on the Europe–Asia axis. On the right, Eskişehir Technical University acts as a bridge at the eastern end through its reciprocal links with Budapest University of Technology and Economics and National Cheng Kung University; this line functions as a strategic connection corridor that strengthens the periphery–center interaction of the network.

Fig. 5: International Cooperation Network in Sustainable Aviation (1990–2025)

Figure 5 shows a modular structure where the international cooperation network features the United States and China as the largest and most highly connected nodes at the center, with the United Kingdom–Germany–Netherlands axis tightly organizing the European cluster. Within the European sub-network, there is intense internal connectivity around Germany and strong bridges via the Netherlands, while on the Asia-Pacific side, Japan, Hong Kong, and the Australia–India line stand out with multiple connections. The east-west backbone of the map consists of thick ties extending from the US–UK–Europe triangle to China; this backbone is the main carrier of global information flow. Regional rising actors, including Türkiye, form transition points extending from the periphery to the center through multiple but thinner ties established with Central/Eastern European nodes. A small number of countries (e.g., the Philippines) are connected by unilateral or limited bridges; for these countries, cooperation intensification strategies have the potential to increase the network's inclusiveness and thematic diversity.

While the co-authorship analysis reveals a clear centrality of the United States, the United Kingdom, and China, the bibliometric results do not allow for direct causal inference. Nevertheless, this network structure is consistent with the presence of large national research systems characterized by high publication volumes, sustained research and development investment, and strong aviation- and energy-related industrial ecosystems. The prominence of these countries in international collaboration networks may therefore reflect structural research capacity and long-standing engagement in multinational scientific projects rather than topic-specific effects alone.

Fig. 6: Common-View Network of Headings–Abstract Terms in Sustainable Aviation (1990–2025)

Figure 6 shows the co-occurrence network of title–abstract terms, revealing the interactions between four main clusters. The central green cluster represents SAF production and cost uncertainties along the “aviation fuel–production–feedstock–price/techno-economic analysis” axis; this cluster is the main connecting bridge of the network. The yellow cluster on the right focuses on chemical process/reactor-oriented studies with terms such as “catalyst–reaction–mixture–aromatic/alkane.” The blue cluster at the top shows engine/combustion and experimental research with terms such as “engine–combustor–flame–ignition–test.” The red cluster on the left represents the business, economic, and policy dimensions with tags such as “airport–airline–economy–risk management–policy support.” The strongest links between clusters are those established by the production–cost core with both process chemistry and engine/combustion testing and airport/airline applications; this structure shows that the thematic flow extends from fuel synthesis to system integration and operational/policy implementation.

The prominence of the production–cost core as a bridge reflects an inherent translation requirement: laboratory-scale conversion routes must be assessed against scalable costs and lifecycle impacts before they can inform deployment and policy design.

4. Discussion

The network maps of this study show that the core of the sustainable aviation literature is concentrated around the axis of fuel technologies–impact assessment–system integration. In particular, the formation of strong bridges between SAF production, LCA/TEA, and engine/combustion testing in the title–abstract and author keyword networks suggests the establishment of a knowledge chain extending from laboratory-scale processes to operational/economic outcomes. Recent reviews confirm this picture: life cycle emissions and unit costs vary widely across different SAF routes (HEFA, FT, ATJ, PtL); factors such as technology maturity, feedstock logistics, and process energy carbon intensity significantly influence the outcomes. Therefore, the combined use of LCA–TEA has become the norm in policy and investment decisions (Borrill et al., 2024).

From an interpretative perspective, the central positioning of the United States, the United Kingdom, and China in the co-authorship network may be explained by a combination of structural capacity and policy-driven dynamics. These countries host extensive research infrastructures supported by substantial R&D funding and benefit from large aviation and energy sectors that facilitate academia–industry collaboration. In recent years, regulatory momentum and long-term decarbonization commitments have further reinforced these dynamics by aligning research agendas with policy priorities. For example, the United States’ Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) Grand Challenge establishes explicit production targets that encourage coordinated research across fuel pathways, supply chains, and lifecycle emissions assessment (U.S. Department of Energy, 2022). Similarly, the European Union’s ReFuelEU Aviation initiative provides a regulatory framework that translates climate objectives into SAF deployment requirements, thereby stimulating both scientific output and cross-border collaboration (European Commission, 2023). At the global level, the adoption of a long-term aspirational goal of net-zero carbon emissions for international aviation has expanded the scope and urgency of collaborative research efforts, particularly in relation to sustainable fuels, emissions accounting, and market-based mechanisms (ICAO, 2022).

At the same time, the network structure highlights the peripheral position of many countries, indicating unrealized potential for broader participation in international research collaboration. Countries with limited co-authorship connectivity may benefit from targeted strategies such as establishing joint projects with hub institutions, participating in international funding schemes, and sharing data and experimental infrastructure, including lifecycle assessment databases, SAF blending test results, and measurement, reporting, and verification (MRV) systems aligned with CORSIA requirements (ICAO, 2019). In addition, engagement in high-visibility conferences, focused special issues, and coordinated project calls may support integration into global research networks and enhance both scientific impact and knowledge transfer.

Beyond descriptive patterns, the maps indicate three analytically relevant properties of the field. First, subfields related to hydrogen/electrification and non-CO₂ operational mitigation appear comparatively fragmented, with weaker integration into the dominant SAF-centered knowledge chain—suggesting parallel research streams that may benefit from stronger cross-citation and joint projects. Second, thematic concentration around the SAF–LCA/TEA nexus signals both maturity and path-dependence: while it accelerates comparability for policy and investment decisions, it may also crowd out exploratory work on operational non-CO₂ mitigation and system-level infrastructure constraints. Third, the persistence of peripheral actors likely reflects cumulative advantage and resource asymmetries (funding, infrastructure access, and participation in multinational programs), reinforcing the need for targeted collaboration mechanisms and shared datasets that lower entry barriers.

The centrality of fuel-based clusters reinforces the weight of SAF scaling in near-term sectoral emissions reductions. NREL's recent ETJ (ethanol-to-jet) study shows that GHG reductions ranging from 26% to 96% are possible with the greening of the electricity/heat source; conversely, increases of 6% to 32% in the minimum selling price may be seen. Such findings explain why the “production–feedstock–price/techno-economic analysis” triangle is so strongly linked in our network and indicate that cost-emission trade-offs will remain on the research agenda (Uddin et al., 2025).

While alternative propulsion nodes (hydrogen and electrification) appear as relatively separate sub-sets in the network, recent literature clarifies the medium-to-long-term potential and technical limitations of these areas. Reviews from 2024–2025 highlight that engineering and infrastructure barriers are critical in hydrogen propulsion, particularly regarding cryogenic storage, volumetric density, and new body-propulsion architectures; that fuel cell hybrid configurations are prominent in the short-to-medium range; while full-scale applications are delayed depending on technology and infrastructure synchronization. This picture is consistent with findings that the industry's time horizon is extending and reinforces the role of SAF as a “bridge solution” in the near term (Soleymani et al., 2024).

The network's operations/economics/policy cluster reflects the importance of operational interventions and market designs in achieving sustainability goals. Recent studies highlight the contribution of non-CO₂ effects (NO_x, water vapor, aerosols, and especially contrail-cirrus) to climate forcing; the thickening of the “airport–airline–risk management–policy support” tags in our network parallels this multidimensional agenda. On the policy front, it is shown that measures such as contrail avoidance and weather-sensitive altitude/time optimizations in flight network planning present a complex cost-benefit surface that must be balanced with fuel consumption. These findings make the role of bridge institutions and countries in collaboration networks strategic, as such interventions require multi-actor data and governance (Lee et al., 2023).

The Europe–North America–East Asia backbone emerging in our institution and country collaboration maps aligns with the findings of recent bibliometric SAF studies: these regions are central not only in publication volume but also in the network's connectivity strength and thematic diversity. However, the bridges observed in our network along the Türkiye–Central Europe–East Asia axis indicate that emerging actors can create niche centers in specific sub-themes (e.g., process chemistry, catalysis, supply chain modeling). This suggests that establishing targeted consortia will be effective for future knowledge flow and technology diffusion (Xu et al., 2025).

Consequently, when we read the current literature together with bibliometric maps, three research directions emerge: (i) LCA/TEA-coordinated studies optimizing raw material-process-energy integration in fuel processes; (ii) system-level assessments addressing architecture, storage, and location infrastructure together in hydrogen/electrification; (iii) interdisciplinary approaches combining meteorology-contextual operational strategies, network planning, and incentive design for non-CO₂ impacts. These orientations increase the importance of bridge nodes seen in our networks and indicate that transdisciplinary collaborations between different theme/continent clusters will determine the pace of sustainable aviation (Yang & Yao, 2025).

5. Conclusion

This bibliometric mapping shows that sustainable aviation research has accelerated significantly since 2019 and that the thematic core has concentrated on SAF production–LCA/TEA assessments–hydrogen/electrification and policy/operations axes. In terms of co-authorship and collaboration networks, the US, UK, and China hold central positions, while at the institutional level, DLR, PNNL, and Washington State University demonstrate strong connections; Eskisehir Technical University stands out as a regional bridge. Collaborations clustered around Heyne and Yang in the author network are driving knowledge production. The findings confirm the interdisciplinary nature of the field, while for the coming period (i) commercial scaling of SAF and feedstock/reactor optimization, (ii) technical-economic feasibility of alternative propellants, (iii) effectiveness analysis of regulatory and market mechanisms, and (iv) data-driven efficiency in airport/airline operations.

From a policy perspective, the bibliometric indicators and network structures presented in this study show that the sustainable aviation literature has evolved from a niche research area, particularly in recent years, to a policy-driven and application-oriented agenda. In this context, policy design can accelerate both knowledge production and real-world deployment when it provides credible long-term demand signals and reduces uncertainty for investors and researchers. Instruments such as SAF blending mandates, incentives, and coordinated target-setting tend to strengthen the research–industry pipeline by translating decarbonization ambitions into measurable uptake trajectories, which in turn stimulates R&D activity and cross-sector collaboration. Moreover, international alignment around long-term climate objectives for aviation should be operationalized through national roadmaps that integrate robust measurement, reporting, and verification

(MRV) infrastructures, enabling consistent emissions accounting and comparability across jurisdictions. Finally, market-based mechanisms should be framed as complementary tools that work in tandem with SAF scale-up and operational efficiency measures, while supply-chain and cost constraints must be explicitly considered in policy sequencing; otherwise, ambitious targets may be undermined by limited feedstock availability, production capacity bottlenecks, and uneven regional access to SAF.

Based on the mapped concentration around the SAF–LCA/TEA core, policymakers should prioritize harmonized lifecycle accounting rules and transparent eligibility criteria to reduce uncertainty and improve comparability across SAF pathways. Given the fragmentation of hydrogen/electrification clusters, targeted mission-oriented programs that connect propulsion R&D with infrastructure and certification research can improve integration and reduce duplication. Finally, to broaden participation beyond core countries, funding calls that require multi-country consortia and open data deliverables (e.g., LCA inventories, blending test datasets, MRV-ready emissions data) can strengthen peripheral nodes and improve network inclusiveness.

Findings regarding limitations and policy/research implications are limited to Scopus-based, English-language records of the “article” type; results may be affected by sensitivity analyses to different databases, languages, and document types, as well as VOSviewer threshold/normalization settings. Finally, the most recent year(s) (2024–2025) may be partially affected by Scopus indexing lags; therefore, short-term trend interpretations should be made cautiously. In addition, the 2025 value reported in this study represents publications indexed as of September 2025 and may be revised upward as further records are indexed.

Author Statement

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Ethical approval

Not applicable.

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